

Effects of Different Nodal Interaction on the Stem Growth of Umzimbeet (*Millettia grandis* S.)

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Abstract

This project examines the effect of different nodal interaction of Umzimbeet (*Millettia grandis*) stem was conducted within the premises of Federal College of Forestry (FRIN), Jericho, Ibadan, Oyo State, using river sand as the only growth medium. The root stock of *Millettia grandis* were collected from its mother plant at the seed section in FRIN, Ibadan. The river sand was washed thoroughly and sterilized to get rid of parasitic organisms present in the soil. There were six (6) treatments in the experiment, replicated five (5) times. Treatments were arranged in a complete randomized design. The root stock was planted in different pots and watered twice a week, data assessment was carried out weekly. At the end of this experiment, it was observed that T₆ sprout and thrive well according to the result of stem diameter having an average of 2.16, T₁ having 11.32 average for leaf count and T₄ with an average of 12.736 according to plant height. The result also shows that to enhance the sprouting of this plant species through stem propagation with the nodal interaction used; T₆ has proven to be the best treatment used and it is recommended as the best treatment.

Keywords: *Millettia grandis*, nodal interaction, FRIN, root stock, parasitic organisms

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Introduction

Tree planting is grounded in forest science, and if performed properly can result in the successful regeneration of a deforested area, because trees remove carbon dioxide from the air as they grow, tree planting can be used as a geo-engineering technique to remove CO₂ from the atmosphere, there are trees for shade and shelter, trees that provide fruits and nuts, ornamental trees and flowering trees, deciduous and evergreen.

They come in all shapes and sizes from tiny dwarfs to the towering Redwoods, windswept bristlecone to whimsical topiary. Trees exist in all but the very driest or coldest regions of the world. (Obiri, 2002).

The genus '*Millettia*' plant appears in the African official book describing medicines and other studies of effect of chemical compounds on living animals and also on the use and effects of medicinal drugs. It is then known that the plant having genus '*Millettia*' is a traditional (local) herbal or medicinal tree which is having a wide range of biological activities such as anti-tumoral, anti-inflammatory, anti-viral, bactericidal, insecticidal, and pest destroying. (Labat, 1995).

The confirmation of the traditional pharmacology activities must be systemized, with reproducible procedures, in order to validate the traditional herbal formulations. The development of increasingly pointed techniques for pharmacology studies can help to widen the therapeutic spectrum of '*Millettia*'. The various species are sometimes difficult to recognize by the local populations (Hutchinson, 1964)

- Family: Papilionaceae (Leguminosae - Papilionoideae, Fabaceae)
- Vernacular names: Umzimbeet, Umsimbithwa (Zulu), Kaffir, Ironwood

Millettia is named after Charles Millet of Canton, China (Daskuki, 1991) and *grandis* means large. This plant belongs to the pea and legume family Fabaceae.

Millettia grandis has a rather small area of distribution. Therefore, it may easily become liable to genetic erosion, although it is still locally common. In many regions it is already under pressure because it is a favored tree for building poles and wood carving and because many forests in its area of distribution are being cleared for agricultural land. However, it seems that Umzimbeet could sustain current levels of exploitation in some forests in South Africa. Umzimbeet occurs in coastal forest and open lowland forest up to 600 m altitude. It can be found as a pioneer along forest margins. It tolerates light frost.

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It often occurs on sandy soils, but also on shale, where trees are often gnarled. It grows best in deep soils where ample water is available. It is locally common. Umzimbeet occurs along the coast from eastern South Africa from North of East London in the Eastern Cape Province into KwaZulu-Natal as far as southern Mozambique (Daskuki, 1991).

Umzimbeet has several features which gives it tremendous agro-forestry potential for rural community development. It does not compete vigorously with other crops and being a Legume, it enhances soil fertility through its nitrogen fixing ability. This plant species tends to be unknown to many people, hence: this study is concerned and based on the research to know how this plant species is being propagated and the effect of the growing medium used in the sprouting of the *Millettia grandis* stem. This is because the plant species is indigenous and it is unknown to many people. Therefore, the study is aimed at determining the effect of nodal interaction for propagating Umzimbeet (*Millettia grandis*) through stem cutting.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Site

The experiment was carried out within the premises of Federal College of Forestry, Ibadan, located within the Government Reserve Area (GRA), Jericho, Ibadan North – West Local Government Area, Oyo State. The area lies between latitude 7°26'N and longitude 3°51'E. The climate pattern is tropically dominated by annual rainfall ranges from 1,300-500mm and average relative humidity of about 65 % the average temperature is about 26°C. The dry season usually commence from November to March while the raining season is usually April to October (FRIN, 2016).

Material Source

The stem of *millettia grandis* were collected from its mother plant at the seed section in FRIN, Ibadan, Oyo state. The river sand was collected from the college stream, where the watering can, hand trowel, secateurs, sieve, bucket were gotten in the college premises, while the polythene pots were gotten from Dugbe market.

Methods

The collected soil [river sand] was washed thoroughly and sterilized in order to get rid of parasitic organisms that might be present in the soil which may affect the growth and sprouting of the plant part. The root stock was planted in different design and were

watered twice in a week because the plant does not require much water during rainy season but it requires much in dry season (ample).

The experimental pots were filled with river and root stock were inserted into it, where the experiments consist of (6) treatments replicated (5) times making it a total of thirty (30) pots and weekly assessment were recorded accordingly.

Experimental Design

The experiment was laid down in a Complete Randomized Design (CRD). The treatments were as follows: -

T₁ = One node interaction

T₂ = Two node interaction

T₃ = Three node interaction

T₄ = Four node interaction

T₅ = Five node interaction

T₆ = Six node interaction

Parameter Accessed

Plant Height (cm) – the plant's height was determined with the use of a tape rule

Numbers of leaves – the number of leaves were counted weekly

Stem diameter – the stem diameter of the plant was measured with the use of Vernier caliper.

Data Analysis

The data obtained were statistically analyzed by two-way ANOVA. Mean differences were calculated for significance by using Duncan's test at $P \leq 0.05$ significant level

Results and Discussion

Table 2 shows that the highest average value according to plant height, T₄ with a value of 12.736, followed by T₆ = 11.412, then T₁ = 10.712 and the least average value; T₅ = 7.128.

Table 1: Physical and Chemical Composition of the Soil Used

Sample Description	River sand
%0.C	0.83
%0.M	0.25
%N	0.04
P (Mg/kg)	4.06
Mn (mg/kg)	1.06
Fe (mg/kg)	2.0
Cu (mg/kg)	2.6
Zn (mg/kg)	11
Na (Cmol/kg)	3.0
K (Cmol/kg)	0.21
Mg (Cmol/kg)	1.06
Ca (Cmol/kg)	0.96
Sand (%)	91.00
Clay (%)	5.0
Silt (%)	4.0

Source: Department Soil Laboratory, Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, 2018

Table 2: Effect of Nodal Interaction on the Plant Height of *Millettia Grandis* Stem.

TRT	Weeks					Mean
	1	2	3	4	5	
T ₁	5.06	7.50	11.00	14.20	15.80	10.712
T ₂	1.28	6.80	9.10	10.60	13.12	8.18
T ₃	3.02	6.60	12.50	14.10	16.18	10.48
T ₄	7.80	10.20	13.50	15.38	16.80	12.736
T ₅	4.38	5.54	7.26	8.42	10.04	7.108
T ₆	11.412	11.60	13.62	15.50	16.34	17.82

Table 3: Effect Of Nodal Interaction on the Leaf Count of *Millettia grandis* stem

TRT	Weeks					Mean
	1	2	3	4	5	
T ₁	6.60	8.00	9.60	13.40	15.00	11.32
T ₂	0.00	3.80	6.00	7.00	10.60	5.48
T ₃	1.60	3.80	5.60	9.40	10.80	6.24
T ₄	2.80	5.60	7.20	8.60	11.80	7.2
T ₅	1.00	1.60	4.20	7.00	10.20	4.8
T ₆	5.60	9.20	10.64	10.80	11.80	12.80

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Table 3 shows that the nodal interaction of *Millettia grandis* reacts to the growth medium used at different value with T₁ having the highest average value of 11.32, followed by T₆, 10.64 and the least average value was T₅ = 4.8.

Table 4: Effect of Nodal Interaction on Stem Diameter of *Millettia grandis* stem

TRT	Weeks					Mean
	1	2	3	4	5	
T ₁	1.160	1.420	1.660	1.900	2.100	1.648
T ₂	1.200	1.540	1.640	1.900	2.020	1.66
T ₃	1.220	1.440	1.640	1.960	1.980	1.648
T ₄	1.400	1.640	1.900	2.100	2.280	1.864
T ₅	1.340	1.460	1.520	1.800	1.980	1.62
T ₆	1.560	1.880	2.140	2.16	2.400	2.820

Table 4 shows that the interaction of the stem on the growth medium used at different value with T₆ having the highest value 2.16, followed by T₄ 1.864, T₁ and T₃ having the least average with the same value 1.648.

Conclusion

At the end of this experiment, it was observed that for the nodal interaction of Umzimbeet (*Millettia grandis*) stem, different treatment responded well with the growth medium used. From the various result in the experiment, it shows that T₆ sprouted and thrived well according to the result of stem diameter but not at the highest level in all; T₁ and T₄ in leaf count and plant height, respectively, also thrived well in the experiment.

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